

THE PROCESS OF PRODUCTION OF ELECTRIC CARS

Shavqiyev Elbek

Student Of The Faculty of Transport of Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

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Annotation: This article analyzes the possibilities of the production of electric cars in Uzbekistan, the existing problems in the establishment of this industry, shortcomings and their solutions, the current situation in developed countries for the production of electric cars, advanced auto concerns, their achievements and disadvantages.

Keywords: battery, inverter, battery, electric converter,

The Uzbekiston automotive industry is currently developing and updating, and from year to year the production of new cars is being established. At the same time, the shortage of fuel observed in our country indicates the need to produce cars operating on alternative fuel types. This in turn indicated the need to manufacture electric cars and re-equip moving cars as electric cars in existing internal combustion engines. Based on the current conditions in our country, the president of the Republic signed a resolution on the development of the industry "on measures for state support for the organization of production of electric cars". According to him: in order to actively introduce "green" technologies into all areas, reduce the volume of harmful gases released into the air by using the production of electric cars and their components:

1. Let the following measures be used to support the industrial production of electric cars and hybrid cars:

a) by January 1, 2030: from the disposal collection of electric cars and hybrid cars produced in the Republic; from the customs duty exemption of components of electric cars and hybrid cars imported from abroad (machinocomplex), raw materials and materials, equipment and technological equipment, including spare parts for servicing, according to the lists formed in the prescribed manner;

b) customs duty and disposal collection of electric cars and hybrid cars to manufacturers for no more than 24 months from the time the project began to be implemented, until the processes of production of electric cars and hybrid cars were mastered in a full cycle, but the analysis of literature on the topic A number of foreign specialists have conducted research on electric cars and the devices used in them.

Including James Larminie, John Lowry (UK), V.E. Yutt, W.I.Stroganov (Russia), L.M.Valentinovna (Kazakhstan), Fulton L, Tal G. and Turrentine T. It is

possible to show the work of (USA) and other scientists. In his research, James Larmini and Assistant Engineer John Lowrys[3], director and senior lecturer of the postgraduate department at the University of Oxford Brooks School of technology, scientific research has been carried out on the possibility of an increase in the contribution of electric drives in the near future in the field of Motor Transport and an increase in the production of electric cars The advanced electric car models produced have been analyzed. V.E. Yutt, W.I.Stroganov conducted several analyzes in his research on the development of vehicles through electric drives and the development of vehicles with combined drives [4]. Fulton L, Tal G. and Turrentine T. in the research carried out by the LAR, the latest trends in the world car market of electric vehicles are studied. The rapid transition of countries around the world to electric vehicles has shown the development of electric cars as dominant in the near future. The Paris Declaration on electromobility in particular (UNFCCC, 2015) calls for the production of 400 million electric cars worldwide by 2030. This article explores the basics of achieving these requirements [5]. L.M.In valentinovna's master's thesis, brogan conducted in-depth scientific research on the development trends of electric cars and the improvement of their characteristics and design. In particular, electrodvigatels, gearboxes, and battery batteries currently in use in electric cars have been scientifically analyzed. In addition, the competitive environment for the production of electric vehicles is currently analyzed in the world economy [7].

In the diploma work of The Bachelor of Tomsk Polytechnic University Bukhtuyev Vadim Yureich, the stages of designing electric cars were fully carried out. In particular, electrodvigatel selection and its weighing are used in the construction of speed characteristics, the selection of battery batteries and their energy capacity, minimum charge cycle, optimal operating temperatures are calculated and studied on the basis of empirical experiments. Lithium-iron-phosphate batteries were chosen as the battery battery, which is precisely the last modern advanced battery[8].

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